

¹⁶ ABSTRACT:

17 Fig. S1. Climatology of omega at 500hPa, divergence of the velocity at 200hPa, and Rossby wave source at
 18 200hPa, for BoM in NDJF the first and second days after initialization.

19 Fig. S2. Climatology of omega at 500hPa, divergence of the velocity at 200hPa, and Rossby wave source at
 20 200hPa, for BoM in NDJF the first and second days after initialization.

21 Fig. S3. Climatology of divergence at 200hPa and Rossby wave source at 200hPa, for HMCR in NDJF the
 22 first and third days after initialization.

23 Fig. S4. As in Figure 2 in main paper but for the difference between the models and reanalysis, with the
24 multi-model mean in thick gray.

25 Fig. S5. As in Figure S4a but contrasting the reanalysis response with the response in each individual ensemble
26 member.

27 Fig. S6. The EN minus LN composite difference in each forecasting system in sea surface temperatures in
 28 the sixth week after initialization for models with a coupled ocean. The mean EN-LN difference in the Niño3.4
 29 region is indicated for each model. The HMCR forecasting system is not coupled to an ocean model and hence
 30 is excluded.

Fig. S7. As in Figure S6 but for the corresponding dates in NOAA daily SST data.

31 Fig. S8. The difference in SSTs between Figure S6 and S7. Note that CNRM and CMA have opposite signed
 32 ENSO biases yet both simulate among the worst biases in the North Pacific response to ENSO.

33 Fig. S9. Standard deviation of 500hPa North Pacific height (boxed region in Figure 1 of main text) in week 6
 34 of December initializations for (thin magenta) each ensemble member; (black) mean of the magenta lines; (thick
 35 brown) corresponding dates in ERA-I reanalysis. The standard deviation is computed for each initialization date
 36 in December separately for each model.

37 Fig. S10. Correlation of Z₅₀₀ in the boxed region of Figure 1 of the paper with omega at 500hPa, divergence
 38 at 200hPa, and Rossby wave source at 200hPa in reanalysis data over the 1981-2013 period covered by the
 39 BoM hindcasts, using the dates associated with week 6 of the December initializations. A positive correlation
 40 between the North Pacific low and tropical omega at 500hPa indicates that a deepened North Pacific low is
 41 associated with negative anomalies in omega (i.e. upwelling), while a negative correlation between the North
 42 Pacific low and subtropical omega at 500hPa indicates that a deepened North Pacific low is associated with
 43 positive anomalies in omega (i.e. downwelling). Similarly, tropical divergence and subtropical convergence at
 44 200hPa are associated with a deepened North Pacific low. While such correlations cannot demonstrate causality,
 45 theory has demonstrated that tropical convective sources lead to the North Pacific low anomalies associated with
 46 ENSO as discussed in the introduction of the main text.

Dec initializations, wk:3
El Nino-La Nina omega500

Fig. S11. As in Figure 3 in main text but for week 3 omega at 500hPa.

Dec initializations, wk:3
El Nino-La Nina div200

Fig. S12. As in Figure 4 in main text but for week 3 divergence at 200hPa.

Dec initializations, wk:3
El Nino-La Nina RWS200

Fig. S13. As in Figure 5 in main text but for week 3 Rossby wave source at 200hPa.

47 Fig. S14. Response of omega at 500hPa to ENSO in KMA December initializations as compared to ERA-I
 48 reanalysis in (a-c) week 1; (d-f) week 3; (g-i) week 6; (j-l) week 8.

Fig. S15. As in Figure S14 but divergence at 200hPa.

Fig. S16. As in Figure S14 but Rossby wave source (RWS) at 200hPa.

U200hPaDec initializations, wk:3

Fig. S17. As in Figure 6 in main text but for week 3 zonal wind at 200hPa.

49 Fig. S18. Ray tracing of the extratropical response to wave-3 launched in the boxed region of Figure 5 of the
 50 main text using the (top) KMA simulated winds in week-5 of December initializations; (bottom) corresponding
 51 winds in ERA-I.

52 Fig. S19. As in Figure 9 in the main text but for week 2 following NDJF initializations during MJO phases
 53 5/6 as compared to MJO phases 1/2.

NDJF initializations, wk:3
MJO 45-MJO 81 omega500

54 Fig. S20. As in Figure 10 in the main text but for week 3 following NDJF initializations during MJO phases
55 4/5. Week 2 is in the main text.

56 Fig. S21. As in Figure 10 in the main text but for divergence at 200hPa for week 2 following NDJF ini-
 57 tializations during MJO phases 4/5. The boxes are shifted 35 to the west as compared to the figure showing
 58 divergence at 200hPa for ENSO.

59 Fig. S22. As in Figure 10 in the main text but for Rossby wave source at 200hPa week 2 following NDJF
 60 initializations during MJO phases 4/5. The boxes are shifted 35° to the west as compared to the figure showing
 61 divergence at 200hPa for ENSO.

62 Fig. S23. As in Figure 11 in main paper but for the difference between the models and reanalysis, with the
63 multi-model mean in thick gray.

64 Fig. S24. As in Figure 12 in main paper but for the difference between the models and reanalysis, with the
65 multi-model mean in thick gray.

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72 be addressed to C.I.G. (email: chaim.garfinkel@mail.huji.ac.il).

73 APPENDIX

74 **Data Statement:** The original S2S database is hosted at ECMWF as an extension of the
75 TIGGE database, and can be downloaded from the ECMWF server [http://apps.ecmwf.int/
76 datasets/data/s2s/levtype=sfc/type=cf/](http://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/s2s/levtype=sfc/type=cf/).

77 **References**